

Oxide Iron Nanoparticles Produced by Laser: Synthesis and Evaluation

Mu'ataz S. Al Hassan

Al-Shatrah University, Thi-Qar, Iraq;

Al Ayen University, Thi-Qar, Iraq

Suggested Citation

Al Hassan, M.S. (2024). Oxide Iron Nanoparticles Produced by Laser: Synthesis and Evaluation. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 233-237.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).18](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).18)

Abstract:

Nd:YAG laser nanosecond pulses are utilized in the liquid laser ablation process to produce oxide iron nanoparticles. In all systems, Nd:YAG pulse lengths of 6 and 10 nanoseconds are employed, with variable energy ranging from 600 to 700 mJ. By using a TEM with the same size distribution, Oxide Iron nanoparticle formation was prevented. Furthermore, it has been found that Oxide Iron typically exhibits nanoparticle sizes of 80 and 120 nm when the same laser conditions are used. Moreover, the temperature distributions of both

Oxide Iron nanoparticles were estimated using the theoretical Mie-Gans model. Additionally, it has been established that the maximum temperature of oxide iron nanoparticles is between 800 and 1200 K, especially when the nanoparticles are made with 10 ns Nd:YAG.

Keywords: *liquid laser ablation, Oxide Iron nanoparticle, theoretical Mie-Gans model, Nd:YAG.*

Introduction

Copper nanoparticles have great interest due to their optical, catalytic, mechanical and electrical properties. Copper is a good alternative material for noble metals such as Au and Ag as it is highly conductive and much more economical than them (Al Hassan, n.d.a; n.d.b). Copper plays an important role in electronic circuits because of its excellent electrical conductivity. Copper nanoparticles are inexpensive and their properties can be controlled depending on the synthesis method. Also in catalyst, the nanoparticles have a higher efficiency than particles (Al Hassan, n.d.b; Buzea, Pacheco, & Robbie, 2007; Mafuné, et al., 2001). Copper nanoparticles are synthesized through different techniques. The most important methods for the synthesis of copper nanoparticles are chemical methods such as chemical reduction, electrochemical techniques, photochemical.

Nanoscale physical, chemical, and biological properties with diameters ranging from 1 to 100 nanometers are the basis for many techniques and scientific discoveries in the field of nanoscience. (Al Hassan, n.d.a). The two most popular ways for developing nanomaterials are top-down and bottom-up. (Al Hassan, n.d.b). In contrast, one-dimensional, two-dimensional, and three-dimensional nanostructures are the three categories into which nanomaterials are separated (Al Hassan, n.d.b; Buzea, Pacheco, & Robbie,). Nanomaterials are made via chemical or physical processes. Among the physical methods used to create NPs are thermal evaporation, sputtering deposition, chemical vapor deposition, physical vapor deposition, and laser ablation, with dry and wet laser ablation being the most often utilized. Furthermore, for the purpose of creating fluid nanoparticles, Pulse Laser Ablation in Liquid (PLAL) requires contact between the laser and the target

(Mafuné, et al., 2001). PLAL is a single-step, top-down method of producing nanoparticles (Kadhim, Gaayied, & Noori, 2012). Among the nanomaterials that can be produced using this approach are elements, precious elements, transistors, nan alloys, oxidation, and magnetic and base shell nanostructures. Kazakevich,

Simakin, & Shafeev, (2006), Al Hassan, (n.d.b), and Dorrnian, Tajmir, & Khazanehfar, (2013) state that no vacuum apparatus is required (Tsuji, et al., 2006). It is possible to create a mathematical model based on previous interactions.

$$T(t) := \frac{2 \cdot F_0}{k} \left[\frac{1}{(\alpha \cdot t)^2} e^{-\left[\frac{z}{2 \cdot (\alpha \cdot t)}\right]^2} - \frac{z}{\pi^2} \frac{1}{2 \cdot (\alpha \cdot t)^2} \left[1 - 1 - (a \cdot b + A1 \cdot b^2 + C \cdot b^3) e^{-\left[\frac{z}{2 \cdot (\alpha \cdot t)}\right]^2} \right] \right] \quad (1)$$

where P K represents thermal capacity in Watts per square meter, Fo indicates acquired energy at the surface in Watts per square meter, and T(t) indicates temperature in Kelvins. a, A1, C, b: (Sasaki, Shimizu, & Koshizaki, 2006) Consistent; K,:thermal permeability mP2 sP1, P t: Time s,z: Depth m, t1: Energy period off s.

Hz and a pulse duration of 10 ns, the second laser runs at 1000 mJ. Using a 10 cm focal length lens, the focussed Nd beam technique is applied to the iron target. The 99% purity level of the iron plates used is high. The plates have to be cleansed with vinegar and filtered water, then sliced into small pieces in accordance with the experimental technique.

Experiment

In order to accomplish the aim of elimination, Nd:YAG and Er:YAG pulsed laser technologies were applied in this investigation. The first laser has a maximum repetition rate of 10 Hz at its greatest frequency and runs at 850 mJ. Its pulse lasts 6 ns. With a maximum repetition rate of 6

Experimental Details

By integrating the size distribution with the temperature theorem, the temperature distribution of iron nanoparticles was ascertained, yielding the subsequent result:

$$T(r1) := \int_r^{r_0} N \cdot D(r1) \cdot \left[\frac{2 \cdot P \cdot (1 - rf) \cdot r1}{6 \cdot 10^3 \cdot v(r1) \cdot k} \left(\frac{1}{(\alpha \cdot t)^2} e^{-\left[\frac{z}{2 \cdot (\alpha \cdot t)}\right]^2} - \frac{z}{\pi^2} \frac{1}{2 \cdot (\alpha \cdot t)^2} \left[1 - 1 - (a \cdot b + A1 \cdot b^2 + C \cdot b^3) e^{-\left[\frac{z}{2 \cdot (\alpha \cdot t)}\right]^2} \right] \right) \right] dr \quad (2)$$

Based on the solutions to equations 1 and 2, Figures 1 and 2 show the relationship between iron nanoparticle size and heat.

Figure 1. For Laser Nanoparticles Having a 10 ns Pulsing Duration and an Energy of 740 mJ, the Relationship between Temperature and Radius is Shown

Figure 2. A Laser with a 6 ns Pulse Duration and 740 mJ Pulse Energy was Used to Monitor the Temperature and Size of Iron Nanoparticles. Comparison is Made between Theoretical Outcomes for Pulse Durations of 10 ns and 6 ns

The table below compares the Fe nanoparticles generated by a 1064 nm laser with pulse lengths of 6 and 10 ns. The high temperature (°C), liquid depth (m), and laser pulse length (m) are all listed in the table.

Table 1. Comparison Table of Pulse Length

Laser pulsed length	Molten depth (μm)	High temperature (C°)
6ns	4	1300
10ns	6	900

The table shows that a temperature increase of 900 K occurs when the laser pulse duration is decreased from 10 ns to 6 ns.

Experimental Results

Iron (Fe) nanoparticles generated by laser ablation with a 6 ns pulse duration and strengths of 700 mJ and 720 mJ, respectively, are depicted in TEM images in Figures 3A and 3B. The findings show that boosting the laser intensity causes a considerable amount of tiny nanoparticle aggregation, which raises the iron nanoparticles' overall sizes. A drop in temperature and thermodynamic pressure causes smaller iron nanoparticles to be released, leading to the production of smaller nanoparticles.

A

B

Figure 3. TEM Pictures of Oxide Iron Nanoparticles, during (A) 700mJ and 720 mJ (B) Pulse Duration of 6 ns

Note: TEM pictures of iron nanoparticles (Fig. 3), during (a) 700mJ pulse duration of 6 ns

Figure 4. The Size Distribution of Iron Nanoparticles Generated by a High-Dispersion Laser with a Fe Wavelength of 1064 nm (Homogeneous Distribution) is Shown by the Histogram from the Iron Plant. The Laser Causes the Creation of Nanoparticles; it has a High Extinction Coefficient. More Temperature and Vapor Pressure also Sid in the Release of Smaller Fe Nanoparticles

Note: TEM spectrum (Fig. 4) of iron nanoparticles generated with a 700mJ power pulse and a 10 ns pulse duration.

The peak is currently located at 760 mJ (414 nm), which is explained by how smaller nanoparticles are formed at high temperatures. The matching

A

B

Figure 5. UVVIS Characteristic Absorption of Oxide Iron Nanoparticle Mixture Primed with 200 Power Laser Pulses (A) 700mJ and (B) 760mJ, Respectively

UV-Vis absorbance values for aluminum (Al) nanoparticles are shown in Figures 5A and 5B. The spectra of each nanoparticle sample were obtained using a Nd laser that operated at 700 and 760 mJ/pulse at 1064 nm. The analysis of the UV-Vis spectra revealed peaks at 429 nm and 50 nm, which were the major dimensions of the iron nanoparticles formed at 700 mJ. Analogous analyses are carried out when aluminum particles are generated with the same laser power.

The UV-Vis characteristic absorption spectra of a mixture of iron nanoparticles exposed to 200 laser pulses are displayed in Figure 5. Laser strengths of (A) 700 mJ and (B) 760 mJ were used to obtain the spectra. These data shed light on the iron nanoparticles' absorption characteristics at various laser power levels.

The presence of a single surface plasmon maximum suggests that the produced nanoparticles, despite having an elliptical form, are almost spherical, even though the absorption spectrum displays two plasmon peaks. It was usually determined that the produced nanoparticles met the Z-potential assessment criteria since their stability fell between +30 mV and -30 mV. With a primary Z-potential value of -49.42 mV, the iron nanoparticles were found to be stable.

Conclusions

Iron nanoparticles with consistent sizes can be produced with stability using laser liquid ablation. These nanoparticles have been found to exhibit higher temperature distributions, indicating that the use of shorter laser pulses may result in even greater thermal effect magnitudes. Our knowledge of nanoparticle growth and behavior is improved by the theoretical model's incorporation of empirical size distribution data.laser ablation.

Acknowledgement

Sponsored by Al Ayen University

References

- Al Hassan, M. S. (n.d.a). Synthesis and modeling of temperature distribution for Si and Ag nanoparticles produced using Nd laser. *Journal of Baghdad University*.
- Al Hassan, M. S. (n.d.b). Synthesis and analysis of gold nanoparticles produced by laser. *Journal of Al-Ayen University*.
- Buzea, C., Pacheco, I., & Robbie, K. (2007). Nanomaterials and nanoparticles: Sources and toxicity. *Biointerphases*, 2(4), MR17–MR71. <https://doi.org/10.1116/1.2815690>
- Mafuné, F., Kohno, J., Takeda, Y., & Kondow, T. (2001). Dissociation and aggregation of gold nanoparticles under laser irradiation. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry B*, 105(38), 9050–9056. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp012042y>
- Kadhim, A., Gaayied, R., & Noori, M. F. (2012). Preparation of gold nanoparticles by pulsed laser ablation in NaOH solution. *Journal of Babylon University, Pure and Applied Sciences*, 22(1), 547–551.
- Kazakevich, P., Simakin, V., & Shafeev, G. A. (2006). Formation of periodic structures by laser ablation of metals in liquids. *Applied Surface Science*, 252(13), 4457–4461. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2005.08.090>
- Dorrnian, D., Tajmir, S., & Khazanehfar, F. (2013). Effect of laser fluence on the characteristics of Ag nanoparticles produced by laser ablation. *Science and Research Branch, Islamic Azad University*, 2013(October), 93–100.
- Tsuji, T., Okazaki, Y., Higuchi, T., & Tsuji, M. (2006). Laser-induced morphology changes of silver colloids prepared by laser ablation in water: Enhancement of anisotropic shape conversions by chloride ions. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry*, 183, 297–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphotochem.2006.04.005>
- Sasaki, T., Shimizu, Y., & Koshizaki, N. (2006). Preparation of metal oxide-based nanomaterials using nanosecond pulsed laser ablation in liquids. *Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology A: Chemistry*, 182(3), 335–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphotochem.2006.02.018>